

THE MAIN CAUSES OF THE CONTENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL DEFORMATION

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ANNOTATION:

This article describes the essence and causes of the pedagogical deformation. Information is given on the manifestations of professional and pedagogical deformation, people who are most prone to professional deformation, initial conditions of deformation, main causes of deformation, positive and negative consequences of professional deformation. Several recommendations are also given about the prevention of occupational deformation.

Keywords: professional deformation, stereotype, personality deformation, prevention, administrative pleasure monotony, emotional exhaustion, management erosion, "Burn out" syndrome, cognitive fatigue

Introduction

In the world education system, special attention is paid to improving the professional competence of pedagogues, professional self-development based on creative approaches. In particular, prevention of professional and pedagogical deformation, deeper study of the system of interpersonal differential relations, "self study" (independent work on oneself), "self control" (self control), "self development" (self-development), "self-confidence" (self-confidence) is important.

The reforms implemented in our country show the results of large-scale changes to raise the education system to a new level and increase its efficiency. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-80 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan" for the years 2022-2026 "to bring the knowledge and skills of teaching staff to the international level" Important tasks such as [1] were defined. This requires the improvement of the preventive system of professional deformity that occurs in the work of the teacher.

The main part

The issue of professional deformity has been studied since the 20s and 30s of the 20th century. In this regard, it is possible to see scientific researches in which the problems related to professional aspiration, ensuring the reliability of work, increasing work ability, as well as situations related to unfavorable conditions in

professional activity have been studied. However, little attention is paid to improving the preventive system of professional deformity. In order to improve the preventive system of professional pedagogical deformation, first of all, it is necessary to study the essence of professional deformation and the reasons for its development.

Deformation - (Latin "deformation" - "disruption", "change") means a change in the shape and functions of the body as a result of external and internal influences. Professional deformation is a negative change that occurs in the cognitive, behavioral and motivational sphere of a specialist as a result of the influence of external and internal factors in professional activity.

Often, the term "professional deformation of the person" (personal deformation) is widely used in the classification of negative changes in the personality. Taking into account the specific characteristics of pedagogical activity, we propose the term "pedagogical professional deformation", as the basis for this is the existence of specific deformations of the teaching profession, as in every profession. Therefore, we interpret the professional deformation that occurs in the activity of a teacher as a phenomenon that causes changes in personal characteristics, a violation of the content of pedagogical activity, professional qualities and pedagogical abilities under the influence of professional activity [2].

In the 1930s, psychotechnician S.G. Gallerstein wrote that the content of professional activity is not related to the performance of one or another task by employees, but to the adaptation of the organism to certain aspects of the profession. There is a continuous interaction between the organism of the worker and external influences. Due to this, deformation is observed not only in the body, but also in the psyche of the employee. The concept of deformation is usually interpreted as a change that affects an organism and creates an important character trait in it.

Professional deformation was initially associated with the spread of professional stereotypes developed by a person to other areas of life, including. Later, unprofessional behavior (behavior outside the profession) and communication began to appear. Many researchers emphasize the emergence and formation of professional deformation in "human-human" professions. For the first time, the term "professional deformation" was introduced by Pitirim-Sorokin as a sign of negative influence. Professional deformation was described by scientists such as S. G. Gellerstein (1930), A. K. Markova (1996), E. F. Zeer (1999, 2003), S. P. Beznosov (2004), R. M. Granovskaya (2010), S. A. Druzhilov (2013). Researchers distinguish professional deformation of the person, professional deformation of activity, professional deformation of labor behavior.

Professional deformations are changes in the teacher's personality, which have a negative impact on the person himself, on the activities performed by the teacher, on the spheres of his life and others. Professional deformations have the strongest impact on representatives of social professions, including the teaching profession [3]. Vocational deformation is a period when a person loses interest in work. In people, this phenomenon is very simple - it is called professional burnout.

According to the researches of E.F. Zeer and E.Ye. Somanyuk, professional deformation takes place in 4 different ways (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Types of professional deformation

Professional deformation can cause both useful and serious problems. Sometimes deformation is really useful, because some purely professional skills can help a lot in everyday life. For example, someone who holds the position of boss can use their skills to organize some family event. A doctor always knows how to provide first aid. Most importantly, do not forget about the boundary between work and life.

Suggestions

Everyone should know that his attitude to work further affects his mental state in order to prevent the development of professional deformation of the personality. It is important to understand what tasks are placed on his shoulders and strictly adhere to these principles. At the same time, always be ready for change. To prevent professional pedagogical deformation, we recommend the following:

1. Carry out regular preventive measures - at least 2-4 times a year. That is: do not forget about self-development, visit cultural centers, do not overwork and give yourself the opportunity to relax, be strict and kind at the same time. Understand these and grow as a person.

2. Direct your energy to the areas of life that bring you the least joy. To do this, you can read books, take care of your health, get rid of unnecessary things and

improve your skills. Otherwise, professional deformity will be a real problem for you and prevent you from living a full life.

3. Educators (employees) often conduct self-diagnosis to prevent professional deformation: develop the ability to self-criticize;

4. Try to reduce the level of emotional exhaustion in your work. Set aside a certain amount of time for work and personal life.

Summary

In-depth mastering of concrete methods and methods helps to prevent the deformation of a person related to his profession. The syndrome of "burning out" can be included in the deformations of such a person. "Burning out" syndrome occurs in various categories of professionals who use private, personal resources in their work. It is characterized by emotional, physical and cognitive fatigue caused by occupational stress. The reason for the emergence of such a syndrome is: personal unsolved problems of the specialist; making high demands from colleagues with little support; consequences of working with groups with low motivation; low work efficiency; stagnation; fear of disclosure of professional knowledge; The reason may be that it is not allowed to teach and promote work experience.

Prevention of occupational deformity is a set of preventive measures aimed at reducing the initial conditions and probability of occurrence of occupational deformity. It is based on mastering the methods of controlling the mind, developing the ability to switch from one type of activity to another, strengthening the will, and most importantly, not giving in to stereotypes, standards, patterns and acting in real time depending on the situation.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.
2. Abdusamiyev Dilmurod Abdunabi ugli "Pedagogical possibilities of preventing professional deformation in the work of a teacher". Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD) Diss. Author Ref. - Namangan 2023
3. Mynbayeva A.K., Anarbek N., Akhmetova G.K. Diagnosis of pedagogical professional deformations: a view from Kazakhstan. International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology (ICEEPSY 2012) Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Volume 69, 24 December 2012, Pages 1289-1294.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042812055243>